

PECHMANN CONDENSATION OF METHYL β -RESORCYLATE WITH SOME β -KETONIC ESTERS.

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Methyl β -resorcyrate has been condensed with ethyl α -chloro and α -benzoyl acetoacetates and with ethyl acetone dicarboxylate in the presence of sulphuric acid. The results obtained show that as in the condensation of methyl β -resorcyrate with ethyl α -alkyl-acetoacetates, the 4-carbomethoxy group in the resorcinol nucleus has only little retarding influence on the Pechmann condensation.

In continuation of the previous work (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 717; 1938, **15**, 383) methyl β -resorcyrate has been condensed with ethyl α -chloro- and ethyl α -benzoyl-acetoacetates and with ethyl acetone dicarboxylate. The products obtained have been found to be methyl 7-hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R=Me), methyl 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (II, R=Me) and ethyl 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin-4-acetate (III, R=Me, R'=Et).

In the case of ethyl α -benzoyl-acetoacetate the acetyl group is split off in the course of the reaction as observed by Pechmann and Hauke (*Ber.*, 1901, **34**, 356).

The constitution of the coumarin esters (I and II, R=Me) has been proved by hydrolysis to the corresponding acids (I and II, R=H) and subsequent decarboxylation of the acids. The decarboxylated products have been proved to be identical with authentic specimens of 7-hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin, prepared from resorcinol and ethyl α -chloro- and ethyl α -benzoyl-acetoacetate.

On hydrolysis, the coumarin ester (III, R=Me; R'=Et) gives the known 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (Shah *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, **14**, 717) instead of 7-hydroxy-6-carboxycoumarin-4-acetic acid (III, R=H; R'=H).

The results obtained show in agreement with our previous work (*loc. cit.*) on the condensation of methyl β -resorcyrate with ethyl α -alkyl-acetoacetates that the 4-carbomethoxy group in the resorcinol nucleus has only little retarding influence on the Pechmann condensation.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Methyl 7-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (I, R=Me).—To a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (5 g.) and freshly distilled ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate (5 g.) sulphuric acid (80%, 45 c.c.) was added with shaking. After keeping the reaction mixture for 20 hours it was added to cold water. The product was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from rectified spirit in colourless glistening needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 218-20°. (Found: C, 53.7; H, 3.4. $C_{12}H_9O_5Cl$ requires C, 53.6; H, 3.4 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative*, prepared as usual by refluxing the ester with acetic anhydride and pyridine, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 169-70°. (Found: C, 54.2; H, 3.6. $C_{14}H_{11}O_6Cl$ requires C, 54.1; H, 3.5 per cent).

The *methyl ether*, prepared by refluxing the acetone solution of the ester (0.2 g.) with fused potassium carbonate (0.5 g.) and methyl iodide (3 c.c.) for 20 hours, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 218-19°. (Found: C, 55.3; H, 3.8. $C_{13}H_{11}O_5Cl$ requires C, 55.2; H, 3.9 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (I, R=H).—The ester (0.5 g.) was shaken up with sodium hydroxide (10%, 15 c.c.) and kept overnight. The next day the solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the acid crystallised from rectified spirit in shining needles, m.p. 265-67° (efferv.). (Found: C, 48.8; H, 3.3. $C_{11}H_7O_5Cl$, H_2O requires C, 48.4; H, 3.3 per cent).

The acid (0.1 g.) was decarboxylated by heating in a sealed tube with water (15 c.c.) for 9 hours at 180-90°. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 240°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-3-chloro-4-methylcoumarin, obtained from resorcinol and ethyl α -chloroacetoacetate, was not depressed. Pechmann and Hanke (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 236°.

Methyl 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (II, R=Me).—To a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (5 g.) and ethyl α -benzoylacetoacetate (6 g.) sulphuric acid (80%, 25 c.c.) was added gradually with shaking. After keeping for 45 hours the reaction mixture was added to cold water. The oily mass which separated partially solidified on keeping in a frigidaire for 2 days. It was filtered, treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and the insoluble portion crystallised from rectified spirit in pale green needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 200-1°. (Found: C, 68.6; H, 4.0. $C_{17}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 68.9; H, 4.1 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 160-61°. (Found: C, 67.6; H, 4.2. $C_{15}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.5; H, 4.1 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid (II, R=H).—The sodium bicarbonate solution from above was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the product crystallised from rectified spirit in pale green tiny needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 285°. (Found: C, 67.7; H, 3.7. $C_{15}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 68.1; H, 3.5 per cent). The acid can also be obtained by keeping the ester with 10% sodium hydroxide solution for about 60 hours.

The acid was decarboxylated by heating in a sealed tube with water as usual. The product was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove undecarboxylated acid. The insoluble portion crystallised from rectified spirit in thin plates, m.p. 242-44°. Mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of 7-hydroxy-4-phenylcoumarin was not depressed. Pechmann and Hanke (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 243-44°.

Ethyl 7-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin-4-acetate (III, R=Me; R'=Et).—To a mixture of methyl β -resorcyate (5 g.) and ethyl acetone dicarboxylate (6.1 g.), sulphuric acid (80%, 45 c.c.) was added with stirring and after keeping for 20 hours the reaction mixture was added to cold water. The product was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution. The insoluble portion crystallised from rectified spirit in glistening needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 194-96°. (Found: C, 58.2; H, 4.4. $C_{15}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 58.9; H, 4.6 per cent).

The *acetyl derivative* was crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m.p. 148-49°. (Found: C, 58.5; H, 4.3. $C_{17}H_{16}O_8$ requires C, 58.6; H, 4.6 per cent).

7-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin-4-acetic Acid (III, R=Me; R'=H).—The sodium bicarbonate solution from above was acidified with hydrochloric acid and the product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters of tiny needles (1 g.), m.p. 184-86° (efferv.). (Found: C, 56.3; H, 3.6. $C_{13}H_{10}O_7$ requires C, 56.1; H, 3.6 per cent).

The acid on decarboxylation by heating to its melting point till the effervescence ceased gave methyl 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (Shah *et al.*, *loc. cit.*), m.p. and mixed m.p. 212-14°.

Hydrolysis of Ethyl 7-Hydroxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin-4-acetate.—The ester (0.1 g.) was heated in a boiling water-bath for 25 minutes with sodium hydroxide (5%, 10 c.c.) and the solution was acidified. The product was crystallised from rectified spirit in tiny needles, m.p. 285°, mixed m.p. with 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (Shah *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) was not depressed.

Attempts were made to hydrolyse the ester by keeping in contact with cold sodium hydroxide for 30-40 hours, but the desired acid 7-hydroxy-6-carboxycoumarin-4-acetic acid could not be obtained, 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid being formed.

All the analyses recorded are micro-analyses.

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